

EXPLORING METHODS TO ENHANCE THE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS USING THE WORKS OF CHARLES DICKENS.

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Abstract. Educators should help students recognize the deep satisfaction that comes from engaging with literary works. Furthermore, by sharing insights and interpretations of selected texts with aspiring English teachers, educators can spark their interest in these works. This article explores strategies for enhancing reading skills and competencies in future English language teachers.

Keywords: reading literary works, developing reading competencies.

Abstrakt. O'qituvchilar o'quvchilarga adabiy asarlar bilan shug'ullanishdan kelib chiqadigan chuqur qoniqishni tushunishlariga yordam berishlari kerak. Bundan tashqari, ingliz tili o'qituvchilari bilan tanlangan matnlarni tushunish va talqin qilish orqali o'qituvchilar ushbu ishlarga qiziqish uyg'otishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarida o'qish ko'nikmalari va malakalarini oshirish strategiyalarini o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: adabiy asarlarni o'qish, o'qish qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish.

Абстрактный. Педагоги должны помочь учащимся осознать глубокое удовлетворение, которое приносит занятие литературными произведениями. Более того, делаясь идеями и интерпретациями избранных текстов с начинающими учителями английского языка, преподаватели могут пробудить у них интерес к этим работам. В этой статье рассматриваются стратегии улучшения навыков и компетенций чтения у будущих учителей английского языка.

Ключевые слова: чтение литературных произведений, развитие читательских умений.

The role of educators in fostering an appreciation for fiction among future elementary English language teachers is unparalleled. By introducing these prospective teachers to Uzbek folklore, children's literature, and other engaging fictional works, teachers can guide them toward enriching extracurricular learning and independent study. Regularly organizing group and individual interviews, discussions, and debates about literary works encourages deeper engagement.

Familiarity with literary examples helps future English teachers improve their memory and concentration, enhances figurative thinking, and boosts literacy. It also enables them to grasp the core themes of artistic works and refine their speaking skills. Such

exposure nurtures analytical thinking, broadens perspectives, and cultivates intellectual and cognitive growth, along with positive moral traits. Through the characters in literary works, aspiring teachers gain insights into respecting the environment and understanding the nuances of human relationships. As they progress in their academic journey, the need for continuous learning becomes increasingly vital. Therefore, teachers should gradually increase the time spent on reading minutes, cooperate closely with parents in this area, and recommend literary works for future English teachers to read according to their age.

Various activities are organized in cooperation with cultural institutions: library hours, trips to museums, participation in exhibitions, participation in readers' contests, staging fairy tales, etc. Based on the orientation of the reading lessons first of all to the personality of future English language teachers, the possibilities of forming interest in the samples of artistic works will be expanded. On this basis, pedagogical tools, methods and methods serving this purpose are presented. They are: 1) Method of personal experience activation. In this, the teacher offers prospective English teachers to enter the situation of the characters of the play. In this process, Prospective English teachers choose specific situations related to their personal lives. Prospective English teachers are tasked with writing about their feelings and experiences and comparing them with those of their classmates. 2) introspective analysis method - is a unique method of teaching works of art to future English language teachers. Certain situations are always described in works of art. These situations are related to human life. It expresses human experiences and penetrates into the hearts of future English language teachers. One of the teacher's tasks is to challenge prospective English teachers to express their personal experiences. 3) Person-oriented theatrical method. This method is to interest future English language teachers in theatrical art work. In this place, it is thought about the use of the elements of dramatization of the artistic work in the formation of interest in the art work in the future English language teachers, in awakening their emotions. With the help of this method, future English language teachers feel the feelings and experiences of the protagonist of the work of art. 4) Method of self-creative expression. With the help of this method, future English

language teachers imagine their place in the world of culture. For this purpose, the teacher should prepare future English language teachers for appropriate participation in various contests and stage performances. In addition, it is appropriate for teachers to use various interactive technologies in reading and education lessons to interest future English language teachers in primary school. Teachers must install Mimio Studios on interactive whiteboards. Various art games can be placed and presented in it. Such technologies increase the effectiveness of reading lessons and develop the interest of future English language teachers in the works of fiction. It should be noted that today there are many interactive technologies that serve to form the interest of future English language teachers in relation to examples of fiction. Teachers play a pivotal role in fostering artistic appreciation, creativity, communication skills, intelligence, and both logical and imaginative thinking in future English language teachers through effective use of fiction in reading lessons. Employing specific methods is crucial to successfully developing an interest in fictional works among these learners.

In school settings, various activities can be implemented during reading lessons and extracurricular sessions to engage future English teachers with artistic works. For instance, debates provide a platform for discussing specific issues related to a previously read literary piece. Such discussions help prospective teachers form a collective perspective on the work. It is important to differentiate between debate and discussion: while discussions involve open-ended exploration, debates focus on resolving a particular issue and are aimed at reaching a concrete conclusion rather than forming a general opinion.

The "Readers' Selection" method involves choosing theatrical plays to engage learners. Regular visits to the library play a key role in fostering an appreciation for artistic works among future English language teachers. During these sessions, aspiring teachers are introduced to fresh examples of children's literature, enriching their exposure and deepening their interest in the literary arts.

Practical classes on book selection will be held. The use of information technology serves to form a special interest in books by introducing future English language teachers to mass media. By exposing future English teachers to examples of

fiction, a special love for books will be instilled in them. It is proposed to use a number of effective methods for formation and development of reading skills in primary school students in foreign experiences. The didactic possibilities of some of these methods are discussed below: Cassil's method. According to him, the teacher or parents stop reading the book at the most interesting part of the work. They say they don't have time to continue their studies at this point, they have other important things to do. In the end, the child wants to know how the life of the hero of the work was and takes the book in his hands. In elementary grades, children who are familiar with the letters of the alphabet try to read the rest of the work by themselves, although they are hesitant. But children who are not yet able to read well are forced to ask for help from other family members or the teacher at school. Then the answer of the family members or the teacher should be as follows: "Okay, I will help, but let's do it this way: I read two paragraphs, you read one!" The children, who are very interested in the development of the event, agree to this proposal. "Ancient peoples" method. It is also called "People of books" (or "People of books" method). According to the essence of the method, the child was not only allowed to read a few lines or even half a page of an interesting work as a reward if he behaved in an exemplary manner, but also prepared cookies with the appearance of a book. The boy received such cookies in honor of the happy event of reading a book, because, in ancient times people accepted reading books as joy and celebration. The child had to remember this every time he picked up a book. If the child does not behave in an exemplary manner, then he is not allowed to read the book. This method is based on when children start reading the book. Most researchers emphasize the advantage of the "Short-term" study method. The advantage of the method is that it is recommended to parents to read with the student for 10 minutes every day before bedtime without tiring him. If this method is followed, the students of the 1st2nd grade of the primary school will have the opportunity to read a book for about 1 hour a week. Reading the work expressively, in a tone appropriate to the character and actions of the characters, making short stops at certain places of the work, and asking the child "What do you think will be the next development of the story" (it is necessary not to scold or rebuke during the conversation), as well as, after reading, it is advisable to organize a

small conversation with the child about the events and events read [5]. "Carefully study the cover of the work" method. Another method recommended by foreign pedagogues is to carefully study the cover of the work. This method is used in the following order: 1) students are required to look at the cover of the work of art, pay attention to the main notes - the author's name, initials, and the name and illustration (decoration) of the work; 2) students examine the cover of the work; 3) students are invited to remember what information they have about the writer or poet who is the author of the work, his works; 4) students provide information about the author and his works; 5) a cartoon or feature film based on the work is watched under the guidance of the teacher; 6) students are given a task to compare the plot of the work and cartoons or feature films based on it; 7) under the guidance of the teacher, the performance of the task by the students is discussed [8]. "Verbal drawing" methodology. In the experience of foreign countries, not only methods, but also methods are based on effective methods in the formation of reading skills in children. One of such methods is the "Verbal painting" method. This method arises in the reader's mind during the process of reading an artistic work and serves to express the description of the images and plots in it [7]. This method is also known as "Word image". It is directed to the development of students' skills to clarify the images according to their specific characteristics with the help of words, according to which the student should not use words, adjectives, verbs that are not used in the process of reading the work to illuminate the images and plots [5].

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